

Some Observations on Partial Demethylation of Biflavonyls

B. K. Handa, K. K. Choxal, (Miss) Talat Mah and W. Rahman

Partial demethylation of cupressuflavone and agathisflavone hexamethyl ethers gave eight components in each case. Three major components obtained in homogeneous form were characterized, as di-, tri-, and tetra-methyl ethers of cupressuflavone by chromatographic and spectral studies. Trimethyl ether of cupressuflavone is being reported for the first time. The isomerization during demethylation under controlled conditions was noteworthy.

Demethylation of monomeric flavonoids under controlled experimental conditions has extensively been exploited for the preparation of partial methyl ethers. Kawano et al.¹⁻³ were the first to use it in the biflavone series. They reported the synthesis of partial methyl ethers of amentoflavone and hinokiflavone.

Recently Natarajan *et al.*⁴ detected (TLC, silica gel; toluene : ethyl acetate : acetic acid, 20 : 4 : 1 as developing solvent system) the presence of cupressuflavone (I), its dimethyl ether (II), tetramethyl ether (IV) and traces of V in the reaction mixture obtained by controlled demethylation of cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether (V). Acetylation of the crude reaction product followed by fractional crystallization, however, gave them only dimethyl ether of cupressuflavone which was characterized as 7,7"-di-*o*-methyl cupressuflavone (II).

In order to obtain an authentic sample of II required in our laboratories for comparison purposes, cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether (V) was subjected to controlled demethylation strictly under conditions as prescribed by Natarajan *et al.*⁴ TLC examination (silica gel, benzene : pyridine : formic acid, 36 : 9 : 5, as developing solvent system⁵) of the reaction product revealed the presence of eight components (Fig. A) which were labelled as 1-8. R_F value considerations and co-chromatography with authentic samples were suggestive of the parent (1)*, mono- (2)*; di- (4), tri- (6) and tetramethyl (8) ethers of cupressuflavone.

1. H. Miura and N. Kawano, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Japan)*, 1967, **15**, 232.
2. H. Miura and N. Kawano, *J. Pharm. Soc. (Japan)*, 1968, **88**, 1489.
3. H. Miura and N. Kawano, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Japan)*, 1968, **16**, 1838.
4. S. Natarajan, V. V. S. Murti and T. R. Seshadri, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 113.
5. K. K. Choxal, B. K. Handa and W. Rahman, *J. Chromatog.*, 1970, **48**, 484.

* These fractions on methylation showed (TLC) the presence of parent and monomethyl ethers of cupressuflavone and agathisflavone.

Fig. A

Chromatogram of partial demethylation of :

- a. Cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether
- b. Agathisflavone hexamethyl ether. Benzene : pyridine : formic acid (36 : 9 : 5) as the developing solvent system.
 1. Mixture of cupressuflavone and agathisflavone (parent)
 2. Mixture of monomethyl ethers of agathisflavone and cupressuflavone
 3. Dimethyl ether of agathisflavone
 4. Dimethyl ether of cupressuflavone
 5. Trimethyl ether of agathisflavone
 6. Trimethyl ether of cupressuflavone
 7. Tetramethyl ether of agathisflavone
 8. Tetramethyl ether of cupressuflavone.

The major components WH_1 , WH_2 and WH_3 (bands 4, 6 and 8 respectively) separated by preparative thin layer chromatography gave the same methyl ether which by spectral studies was characterized as cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether. R_F values, m.p.s. and mass spectra of acetates of WH_1 , WH_2 and WH_3 are given in Table I. The results of NMR studies showing acetoxy and methoxy shifts of the acetates are recorded in Table II

TABLE I

Compound	R_F value	Mass Spectrum		m.p. (acetate)
		Base peak	(M^+)	
WH_1	0.50	566	734	276°
WH_2	0.60	580	706	265°
WH_3	0.76	594	678	165°

TABLE II

NMR signals of methoxyl and acetoxy resonances in CDCl₃

Compound	Assigned position in biflavone nucleus					
	4'	4''	5	5''	7	7''
WH ₂ tetra acetate	7.78	7.78	7.50,	7.50	6.16	6.16
WH ₂ triacetate	7.73	6.22	7.48,	7.48	6.16	6.16
WH ₃ diacetate	6.22	6.22	7.48,	7.48	6.16	6.16
Hexa-o-methyl cupressuflavone	6.25	6.25	5.88	5.88	6.15	6.15
Hexa-o-methyl agathisflavone	6.22	6.26	5.95	6.41	6.12	6.14

The values are on γ scale, TMS as an internal standard. Numbers in parentheses represent values for acetoxy groups.

WH₁, WH₂ and WH₃ are thus assigned the structures of 7,7''-di-o-methyl cupressuflavone (II), 4',7,7''-tri-o-methyl cupressuflavone (III) and 4',4'',7,7''-tetra-o-methyl cupressuflavone (IV) respectively. The compound III constitutes the first report of trimethyl ether of cupressuflavone.

	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅
Cupressuflavone (I)	H	H	H	H	H	H
7,7''-Di-o-methyl cupressuflavone (II)	Me	H	Me	H	H	H
4',7,7''-Tri-o-methyl cupressuflavone (III)	Me	Me	Me	H	H	H
4',4'',7,7''-Tetra-o-methyl cupressuflavone (IV)	Me	Me	Me	Me	H	H
Hexa-o-methyl cupressuflavone (V)	Me	Me	Me	Me	Me	Me

Agathisflavone (VI)

R = H

Hexa-o-methyl agathisflavone (VII)

R = Me

The other significant observation was the occurrence of isomerization during demethylation experiment under identically controlled conditions⁴. R_F value considerations⁵ of components 3, 5 and 7 indicated the presence of di-, tri- and tetramethyl ethers of agathisflavone (VI). They were combined and subjected to methylation. The methylated product so obtained was characterized as agathisflavone hexamethyl ether (VII)⁶ by IR and NMR studies (Table II).

Agathisflavone hexamethyl ether (VII) under similar conditions gave a mixture of partial methyl ethers of agathisflavone as well as of cupressuflavone (Fig. A). The chromatogram (TLC) of the reaction mixture of VII was identical with that of cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether (V) indicating demethylation as well as isomerization.

The demethylation seems to proceed in the order $5 > 4 > 7$ which is similar to that reported for mono- and biflavonyls¹⁻³. It is noteworthy that the isomerization from C8-C8" to C6-C8" and vice versa under controlled conditions⁴ (100° for 1 hr) proceeds with equal ease whereas under drastic conditions^{7,8} (130-140° for 8 hr) the C6-C8" isomer is a more favoured one⁷. It appears that under the former conditions the reaction is kinetically controlled whereas under the latter conditions it is thermodynamically controlled.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the mps are uncorrected. Preparative thin layer chromatography was done on silica gel G (E. Merck) using benzene : pyridine : formic acid (36 : 9 : 5) as developing solvent system.

Partial demethylation of cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether: A mixture of cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether (500 mg), m.p. 295°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +35$, hydriodic acid (8 ml; d, 1.7), phenol (0.5 ml) and acetic anhydride (1.5 ml) was heated at 100° for 1 hr and poured into ice cold sodium thiosulphate solution (5%, 200 ml). The yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with water, and dried. It was separated into eight components (1—8) by preparative thin layer chromatography. The fractions 4, 6 and 8 were labelled as WH₁, WH_v and WH₃.

4',4'',5,5''-Tetraacetoxy-7,7''-di-o-methyl cupressuflavone: WH₂ (50 mg) was acetylated with pyridine (1 ml) and acetic anhydride (1 ml). The acetate crystallized from CHCl₃-EtOH in the form of colourless needles (30 mg), m.p. 276°. NMR τ p.p.m. : 7.80 (s,6H, OAc-4',4''); 7.52 (s,6H,OAc-5,5''); 6.18 (s,6H,OMe-7,7'').

Hexa-o-methyl cupressuflavone: WH₁ (35 mg) was methylated with methyl iodide (1 ml) and potassium carbonate (1 g) in acetone (100 ml). It was purified by preparative thin layer chromatography and crystallized from CHCl₃-MeOH as fine colourless needles (20 mg), m.p. 299°, R_F 0.43. NMR τ p.p.m. : 6.25 (s, 6H,OMe-4',4''); 5.88 (s,6H, OMe-5,5''); 6.15 (s,6H,OMe-7,7''). $[\alpha]_D^{25} \pm 0$.

6. A. Pelter, R. Warren, J. N. Usmani, R. H. Rizvi, M. Ilyas and W. Rahman, *Experientia*, 1969, **25**, 351.
7. A. Pelter, R. Warren, B. K. Handa, K. K. Chexal and W. Rahman, presented at the 2nd Indo-Soviet symposium on "Chemistry of Natural products including pharmacology", N.I.S. New Delhi, Feb. 2-6, 1970.
8. K. Nakazawa, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Japan)*, 1968, **16**, 2503.

Complete methylation of WH_2 and WH_3 by the procedure as described earlier gave the same product. It was characterised as cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether by its identical chromatographic and spectral behaviour with that of an authentic sample.

4''',5,5''-Triacetoxy-4',7,7''-tri-o-methyl cupressuflavone : WH_2 (50 mg) was acetylated with pyridine (1 ml) and acetic anhydride (1 ml.) The acetate crystallized from $CHCl_3$ -EtOH in the form of colourless needles (30 mg), m.p. 265° . NMR τ p.p.m. : 7.73 (s,3H,OAc-4'); 6.22 (s,3H,OMe-4''); 7.48 (s,6H,OAc-5,5''); 6.16 (s,6H,OMe-7,7'').

5,5''-Diacetoxy-4',4''',7,7''-tetra-o-methyl cupressuflavone : WH_3 (55 mg) was acetylated with pyridine (1 ml) and acetic anhydride (1 ml.). The acetate crystallized from $CHCl_3$ -EtOH in the form of colourless needles (35 mg), m.p. 165° . NMR τ p.p.m. : 6.22 (s,6H,OMe-4',4'''); 7.48 (s,6H,OAc-5,5''); 6.16 (s,6H,OMe-7,7'').

Hexa-o-methyl agathisflavone : A mixture of fractions 3.5 and 7 (ca. 40 mg) was methylated with methyl iodide (1.5 ml) and potassium carbonate (1 g) in acetone (150 ml). It was purified by preparative thin layer chromatography to give a homogeneous product which crystallized from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH as fine colourless needles (20 mg), m.p. 242° , R_F 0.45, $[\alpha]_D^{25} \pm 0$. NMR τ p.p.m. : 6.22 (s,3H,OMe-4'); 6.26 (s,3H,OMe-4''); 5.95 (s,3H,OMe-5'); 6.41 (s,3H,OMe-5); 6.12 (s,3H,OMe-7); 6.14 (s,3H,OMe-7'').

Methylation of bands 1 and 2 separately gave a mixture of cupressuflavone and agathisflavone hexamethyl ethers (TLC) in each case.

Partial demethylation of agathisflavone hexamethyl ether : A mixture of agathisflavone hexamethyl ether (100 mg), m.p. 152° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} +30$, hydriodic acid (1.5 ml; d, 1.7), phenol (0.1 ml) and acetic anhydride (0.3 ml) was heated at 100° for 1 hr and poured into ice cold sodium thiosulphate solution (5%, 200 ml). The separated solid was filtered, washed with water and dried. The chromatogram (TLC) of the reaction product was identical with that obtained earlier by the partial demethylation of cupressuflavone hexamethyl ether.

The authors wish to put on record their deep sense of gratitude to Dr. S. M. Fazlur Rahman, Head, Department of Chemistry, for providing research facilities and to Dr. N. Kawano (University of Nagasaki) for NMR spectroscopy. Two of us (BKH and KKC) also thank the Department of Atomic Energy for financial assistance.